

INFORAC/UNEP-MAP

Agreement between Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA) and National Research Council (CNR) - Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment (IREA)

Types of users and requirements

Report R0

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1 Summary

The 3 activities carried out under phase 0 of the agreement to study, design and define methodologies and technologies related to the development of the UNEP-MAP Knowledge Platform (KP) are described here.

The information sources are selected and described for defining future workflow within KP and users privileges and their roles are described for design implementation of Dashboard, GeoStories and Knowledge Hub.

2 Introduction

This deliverable is in the framework of the agreement between Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA) and Consiglio Nazionale per le Ricerche (CNR) - Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment (IREA) (No. 0003070/2022). In this agreement the Parties undertake to jointly develop study and research activities aimed at defining a strategy for the management and dissemination of knowledge in the Mediterranean area, with reference to a feasibility study, design and definition of methodologies and technologies related to the development of the UNEP-MAP Knowledge Platform (KP) through innovative tools based on the different and complementary competences of INFO/RAC and CNR-IREA

Following the agreement, the phase 0 was divided into two tasks: task 0.1 - concerning the selection of data, definition of users, and their roles; task 0.2 - where the focus was on formalising project and users' requirements.

In the next pages the different activities will be described, starting from the list of the information sources, screening of the available data, and requirements definition with the description of scenarios or workflows for different users.

3 Information sources

The information sources were selected by ISPRA, which identified those websites and relative documents deemed important to be included in the future KP.

To fully describe, classify and order the different data sources (collection of information items), several dimensions (fields) have been proposed (table 1).

Field	Description
Title	Title or name of the data source
URL	Link to the data source
URL service	One or more links to reach the data by requests to a machine to machine interface (e.g. Open Geospatial Consortium - OGC services request, Application Programming Interface - API) or textual description of how and if the data are reachable
API documentation	Where possible a description about API interaction
Item type	Type(s) of the contained resources. It indicates if the content is a document or data of other types (e.g. Geographic vector layer).
Format	Format of the contained data (e.g. png; GeoJSON; ESRI Shapefiles; CSV; GML; KML)
Description	Textual description of the data source
Owner	Institution that maintains the data source
Provider	Institution that provides the data within the data source
Contact Point	e-mail address or link of the contact point
Access rights	Type of access rights to the data within the data source (e.g. public, restricted access)
Theme/topic	Theme that describes the data within the data source (e.g. biodiversity, pollution)
Keywords, tags, free text	Some keywords that allow tagging the data source
Numerosity	Number of items present in the data source during the analysis
How to exploit?	The way how to integrate the data present in the data source within the KP
Access mode/granularity	Description of access mode
Note	-
Expected users	Users that would likely access the data source

Table 1 - The fields used to describe the data sources involved in the analysis. The title of different fields, a brief description of each is listed.

Among other things, the collection of information on these data sources, made it possible to estimate the actual amount of the items (more than 10000), mainly files, to be processed within KP. It was also possible to establish that most data sources (20 out of 24) contain documents, and 3 of these resources also share images and tables, while only 3 out of 24 provide geographical layers. It should be noted here that most documents are in PDF format.

As far as the theme or topic resources they are dedicated to 3 topics: law, regulation, and sea management (13 of 24), pollution (7), and biodiversity (2).

Finally, it can be observed that 21 of the classified repositories have public access, while the remaining 3 are private or provide restricted access.

The table containing all the information collected, can be found and consulted at this link: https://cnrsc.sharepoint.com/:x:/r/sites/UNEP-MAP/Documenti%20condivisi/General/UNEP-Map/Fase0/information_sources_F0-T01.xlsx?d=w970e672311ce4771b797a1685661bd2b&csf=1&web=1&e=1fplaY

4 User type profiling

The users profiling and the user requirements definition (table 2) was the second action realized during phase 0.

Users were defined based on the knowledge of the community, but mainly based on the types of users present in geographic software previously installed and already in use for data management. It was thus possible to define three types of users with different privileges: general, staff, and administrator. The table 2 shows which privileges each user type can have in the Knowledge Hub (KHub), also depending on whether they belong to a particular organization. This shows that Contracting Parties (CPs) and users belonging to Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP) Coordinating Units (CUs) and Regional Activity Centres (RACs) have staff privileges and can upload data, can search, view and download data that are public, and can edit or delete only the data they upload. In the opposite, MAP partners, deemed to be Stakeholders or researchers, despite having staff privileges, may neither upload nor edit content. Anonymous users only have search privileges and may only view public data or content. Finally, from among the Information and Communication RAC (INFO/RAC) staff, system administrators will be chosen.

Users		Access level	Type of registration	Can Upload?	Can Edit/Delete?	Can Search?	Can View?	Can Download?	Can Set Privileges?
Contracting Parties (CP)		staff	Complete	Yes	Yes, their data	Yes	Yes. Public and restricted material (following sharing regulations)	Yes. Public and restricted material (following sharing regulations)	No
Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP) components	MAP Coordinating Unit (CU) and Regional Activity Centres (RACs)	staff	Complete	Yes	Yes, their data	Yes	Yes. Public and restricted material (following sharing regulations)	Yes. Public and restricted material (following sharing regulations)	No
	Information and Communication (INFO) RAC	administrator	Complete	Yes	Yes, all the material on platform	Yes	Yes, all the material on platform	Yes, all the material on platform	Yes
MAP partners	Stakeholders and researchers	staff	Complete	No	No	Yes	Yes, Public and restricted material (following sharing regulations)	Yes, Public and restricted material (following sharing regulations)	No
Other users	anonymous	general	potential/light	No	No	Yes	Yes, only public material	Yes, only public material	No

Table 2 - Users and their privileges for the management of a generic KHub.

5 Use cases

The activities described above were performed as preliminary activities to define use cases of different users that will interact in the KHub. Four user roles have been identified:

- the administrator of the KHub who must be able to manage all other user accounts by associating them a role, and all resources and contents to be included in the KHub;
- citizens who can freely access the contents, documents, maps etc., made available to them through the graphic user interface of the KHub that allows them to visualize, search, and navigates all contents;
- the decision maker, like a public or a private administrator, who is a stakeholder of the KHub and needs to retrieve and analyse documents and maps to perform an informed decision. Beside the functions of the citizen's role, he can register to have a dedicated account that allows her/him to save search results for later use in future sessions;
- the RAC researcher that beside the functionalities available to a decision maker can also upload maps and metadata of documents to be added to the collection managed by the KHub.

In the following the UML use case diagrams for each role are illustrated. In the UML diagram each user, indicated by a man-shaped icon on the left side of each image, can perform specific actions (first ellipsis level). Thus, for example, the Administrator can “creates/links sources”, “creates roles ...” or “manages accounts”. Each action can then “include” one or more sub-actions, which are indicated, again as ellipses, but are placed at a second or third level. In the right side, again as man-shaped icon, this time, non-human users, typically programs, also perform actions. Only through

them can human users complete their operations.

Figure 1 - UML use case diagrams about administrator role of KHub.

Figure 2 – UML use case diagrams about citizen role of KHub.

Figure 3 – UML use case diagrams about decision maker/stakeholder role of KHub.

6 Conclusions

The work carried out during Phase 0 first made it possible to list the sources and related data to be collected and distributed through the KP. The analysis made it possible to realise that these are mainly open access documents and that few are the spatial or numerical data that will have to be processed by the KP.

The privileges identified and listed (Table 2) make it possible to distinguish the different users who will be able to access or upload data through the KP. The roles and workflows identified and described (Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4) are related to users such as administrator, Decision Maker/Stakeholder, Citizen and RAC/researcher that can be mapped against those listed in Table 2 as follows:

Have a role of ...	Have a privileges of ...
Administrator	MAP Components of INFO/RAC
Decision Maker/Stakeholder	MAP partners or CP
RAC/researcher	MAP CU and RACs
Citizen	Other users - Anonymous

From these initial evaluations, it can be concluded that the packages, Dashboard, GeoStories and KHub, that will be developed, will have to be capable of handling both spatial and, above all, document-type data (PDF, Word, images, etc.) and have user management functionalities that allow specific roles with specific privileges to be distinguished.